

PAX 9 Gene - Its Role in Dentistry

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Abstract

Background: PAX 9 gene (Paired box 9 gene) is an important member of the homeobox genes. They are important transcription factors which help in conversion of DNA into RNA and are key regulators of developmental processes such as regional specification, patterning and differentiation of a developing individuals. PAX9 proteins are expressed in the pharyngeal pouches, developing vertebral column and neural crest derived mesenchyme of maxillary and mandibular arches, contributing to palate and tooth formation. **Aim:** This narrative review was conducted to understand the role of PAX9 gene in various orodental diseases and its future scope. **Methods:** Research publications were searched on search engines such as Scopus, Pub-Med, and Google Scholar, and articles with terms such as “PAX9 gene, oligodontia/ hypodontia, class II div 2 or class III malocclusion, tooth impactions, cleft lip and palate” were collected. **Results:** A total of 35 articles were collected and they were further used to formulate this review. **Discussion:** PAX9 gene was found to have a role in development of orodental diseases, especially in: (i) Dental agenesis, (ii) Class II div 2 Malocclusions, (iii) Class III malocclusion, (iv) Cleft lip and palate, and (v) Impaction of teeth.

Key words: PAX9 gene, Dental agenesis, class II and III malocclusions, cleft lip and palate.

Introduction

Humans possess approximately 30,000 genes, and recent advancements in genetics have significantly broadened our understanding of this field. The causes of various oro-dental diseases have long been debated, particularly regarding whether their origins are primarily environmental or genetic.¹ With the progress in genetics and molecular biology, new techniques have emerged that provide deeper insights into the etiology and pathogenesis of numerous human diseases, including those affecting the oral and dental regions. Conditions such as periodontitis, tooth agenesis, cleft lip and palate, dental caries, and various malocclusions have all been shown to have genetic associations.² Genes such as MSX (Muscle Segment Homeobox), PAX (Paired Box Gene), Cathepsin C, AMELX (Amelogenin X-linked Gene), ENAM (Enamelin), and RUNX2 (Runt Related Protein) have been implicated in dental disorders.²

Among these, the PAX9 gene stands out for its critical role in dental development. PAX9 gene belongs to transcription factors family (homeobox genes) which is characterized by DNA binding domain known as paired domain, which is a conserved amino acid motif and has DNA binding activity.³ This gene plays

a crucial role in organogenesis by triggering cellular differentiation. PAX9 is expressed in mesenchyme derived from neural crest cells and plays a crucial role during development of the craniofacial structures and teeth.⁴ The gene is located on the long arm of chromosome 14 (14q13.3)⁵, and it has been reported that mutations in this gene tends to cause various oro-dental diseases.

The PAX9 gene is one of the most extensively studied genes involved in dentition development. Its proteins act as signaling factors during the initiation, bud, and cap stages of tooth development, any mutations in this gene likely to result in dental agenesis (congenital absence of teeth).⁶ Beyond its traditional role in tooth development, recent research has revealed that mutations of PAX9 gene has caused a wide range of other dental issues, such as maxillary canine impactions, cleft palate, Class II Division 2 malocclusions, and Class III malocclusions. Understanding the implications of PAX9 gene mutations is invaluable for clinicians in patient diagnosis,

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treatment planning, and prognostic assessments. By integrating this knowledge into clinical practice, clinicians can create personalized treatment plans, predict possible complications, and enhance overall care of the patient.

Methods

Research publications were searched for 6 months on various search engines such as Scopus, PubMed, and Google Scholar, and articles with terms such as "PAX9 gene, oligodontia / hypodontia, class II div 2 or class III malocclusion, tooth impactions, cleft lip and palate" were collected. Further, all those articles were analyzed to find out the various mutations of PAX 9 gene which can lead to orodental diseases.

Results

32 articles were collected and they were used to formulate this review.

Discussion

PAX9 (Paired box gene) is a member of paired box transcription factor family and includes an octapeptide, two paired box domains (N-terminal subdomain [NSD], linking peptide, C-terminal subdomain [CSD]), and a 128-amino acid paired type homeodomain. It is essential for the formation of dental mesenchyme throughout all stages of odontogenesis. Consequently, mutations in PAX9 gene can lead to abnormal or diminished regulation of proteins, which is crucial for normal development. The PAX9 gene is composed of five exons (1 to 5), with Exon 2 accounting for 61.11% of the coding sequence.⁷ This exon encodes the paired box domain, which is an evolutionary conserved area of DNA binding domain.

Mutations in paired domain can impact binding activities of DNA, stabilization of protein, and activation of other related genes. The PAX9 gene is crucial for the formation of the medial nasal process, palatal shelf, and maxilla. Loss of PAX9 gene function can lead to hypodontia, oligodontia, clefts of the palate, and some skeletal abnormalities. Mutations in the PAX9 gene can range from single nucleotide substitutions which results in amino acid changes, premature termination of translation, and loss of function of the protein and lead to haploinsufficiency.⁸

Additionally, the PAX9 gene is also associated with various orodental issues, including dental agenesis, various mal-occlusions, canine impactions, and cleft lip and palate.

Role of PAX9 Gene In Dental Agenesis

Most common outcome of PAX9 mutation is non syndromic dental agenesis. Tooth agenesis, also known as congenitally missing teeth, is one of the most common congenital abnormalities in man, and it can affect mastication, speech, aesthetics, and can also cause malocclusion.⁹ Tooth agenesis is classified as hypodontia (lack of one to five permanent teeth, excluding the third molars), oligodontia (lack of six or more permanent teeth, excluding the third molars), or anodontia (complete lack of teeth) on the basis of the number of missing teeth.¹⁰

Molecular studies across different populations have identified several gene mutations linked to the congenital absence of permanent teeth, including AXIN2, EDAR, FGFR1, GREM2, IRF6, LRP6, MSX1, PAX9, and WNT10B.¹¹ To date, highest number of etiological mutations has been found in PAX9 gene, which encodes a transcription factor crucial for the development of various organs and skeletal elements, including teeth. PAX9 is expressed in dental mesenchyme at initiation, bud, cap, and bell stages of odontogenesis.¹² Proteins function as transcription factors that facilitate communication between epithelial and mesenchymal tissues, playing a vital role in establishing the odontogenic

potential of the mesenchyme.¹³ Therefore, any mutation in this gene can lead to orodental anomaly. PAX9-deficient mice have shown lack teeth and also pharyngeal pouches derivatives structures were affected. Mutant mice have severe craniofacial anomalies, and were unable to survive due to malformation of secondary palate. Permanent molars are most frequently affected by defects in PAX9 gene also the size of teeth was found to be reduced. Stockton DW et al¹⁴ was the first one to describe mutation in human PAX9 gene as insertion of an additional G allele within the paired box sequence at nucleotide 219 of exon 2 in a family with oligodontia which causes pre-mature termination of translation. Over the years, more than 50 mutations have been found in PAX9 gene in connection with dental agenesis¹⁵ It was also observed that due to PAX9 mutations more missing teeth were seen in maxillary arch when compared to the mandibular arch.¹⁶

Role of PAX 9 Gene In Malocclusions

Development of craniofacial structures is widely believed to be influenced by both genetic and environmental factors. Changes in genes crucial for craniofacial development has affected the development of craniofacial abnormalities. After detecting the association of PAX9 gene in dental agenesis researchers start to investigate its association with class II div 2 malocclusion as dental agenesis is common in this malocclusion. Mathew D Wall¹⁷ found the association between SNP (Single Nucleotide Polymorphism) Marker rs8004560 with individuals suffering from class II div 2 malocclusion and hypodontia. Later similar results were seen by Morford et al¹⁸ in 2010 and it was found that rs8004560 may have a role in class II/D2 mal-occlusions.

In contrast Ghergie, et al¹⁹ when conducted a study on various malocclusion and their association with PAX9 gene it was found that SNP (rs8004560) polymorphism was associated with Class I malocclusion patients rather than class II div 2 malocclusion. Later a study was conducted on Malaysian population by Saad et al²⁰ in which they found no association between PAX9SNP (rs8004560) and Class II skeletal base malocclusion contributed by mandibular retrognathism but they concluded that there is a gray area which need to be researched. PAX9SNP (rs8004560) could be detected and the distribution of genotype and allele could be determined in study with bigger sample size.

Along with association of class II div 2, class III malocclusion association with PAX9 gene have also been studied. Baker et al²¹ conducted a study on individuals with class III malocclusions and found over representation of PAX9 (rs8004560) in the individuals with mandibular prognathism (MP) indicating the genetic association of PAX9 (rs8004560) SNP in the incidence of Mandibular prognathism. Another study was conducted by Rodrigues et al²² to assess if there is any association between polymorphisms in genes causing tooth agenesis and craniofacial patterns. It has also been said that the chance of presenting skeletal class III malocclusion increased by two folds due to the presence of at least one g allele. However, no association was found between PAX9 gene and skeletal craniofacial pattern.

Role of PAX9 Gene In Canine Impaction

The etiology of impacted canine is multifaceted and encompass various factors, such as environmental input (e.g., trauma), local factors (e.g., lack of space, retention of primary teeth, trauma to permanent tooth buds and the presence of pathological lesions, such as dentigerous cysts or odontoma), genetic factors, and systemic disease.²³ Impacted teeth are frequently found in the maxilla, particularly the canines and incisors, as well as in the mandible, including the third molars and second pre-molars.

Among these, second most commonly impacted teeth are maxillary canines with approximately two thirds being impacted on the palatal side.

Peck et al²⁴ first contributed the biologic evidence pointing towards genetic factors as the primary origin of most palatally displaced canines. Decades later in 2019 Devi and Padmanabhan²⁵ found the rs2073247 polymorphism of the PAX9 gene, heterozygous genotype CT was positively associated with palatal impaction of maxillary canines. It has also been suggested that individual's with genotype CC located on SNP 3 (rs12881240) and SNP 4(rs4904210) of PAX 9 gene carried a greater risk for maxillary canine impaction.²⁶

Role of PAX9 Gene In Cleft Lip and Palate

Orofacial clefts are widely acknowledged as prevalent congenital maxillofacial abnormalities globally, affecting approximately 1 in 700 live births (Dixon et al., 2011). Initially, when cleft lip and palate were first documented a century ago, they were attributed to supernatural malevolent forces. However, with advancements in genetic and genomic analysis, there has been significant progress in comprehending the underlying causes of these conditions. Similar to the embryonic development of other organs, palatogenesis from its inception to completion is meticulously regulated, overseen by a complex interplay of genes, tissue interactions, and environmental factors.

Peters in 1998²⁷, was the first to display that PAX9 mutant mice was associated with cleft palate also the development of teeth was arrested at bud stage and mice was not able to survive after birth. The PAX9 gene, which encodes a transcription factor found in both mesenchymal and epithelial cells, exhibits a dynamic expression pattern during palatogenesis. Initially, PAX9 was observed in the epithelium of the murine foregut at embryonic day 8.5 (E8.5).²⁸ By E14.5, there is a decrease in mesenchymal PAX9 expression, while it remains present in the medial edge epithelium (MEE). Between E14.5 and E15.5, epithelial PAX9 gradually diminishes as the midline epithelial seam (MES) disappears and the shelves fuse.²⁹ The distribution pattern of PAX9 varies in accordance with the progression of developmental events.

Palatal shelves in mutant cases exhibit an unusually widened shape on the nasal side, accompanied by reduced mesenchymal proliferation particularly in the middle and posterior regions which result in deficient elongation of shelves.³⁰ At E14.5, delayed elevation is observed on one or both sides of the PAX9 mutant shelves. Subsequently, in PAX9 mutants, the palatal shelves fail to fuse and exhibit irregular and poorly developed palatal rugae. Years later, it was discovered that in cleft embryos, PAX9 expression persists in the medial edge region without down regulation by E15.5, whereas PAX9 expression is down regulated in paired palatal shelves.³¹ Consequently, altered PAX9 expression in spontaneous cleft lip and palate disrupts the fusion of palatal shelves during embryonic development

When compounded effect of mutations in the PAX9 and MSX1 was researched in double homozygous mutants by Nakatomi et al³², it was suggested combined reduction of PAX9 and MSX1 gene dosage in humans may increase the risk for oro-facial clefting and oligodontia. Till date various SNPs of PAX9 gene have been detected which has shown a positive exhibited significant association with non-syndromic cleft lip.

Conclusion

PAX9 gene plays an intricate role within the realm of dentistry, shedding light on its significance in odontogenesis and craniofacial development. The PAX9 gene's pivotal role in dental development

has been elucidated, highlighting its involvement in the formation of teeth and associated structures. Its regulatory functions in odontogenesis, including tooth morphogenesis and differentiation, underscore its indispensable contribution to dental patterning and growth. Furthermore, the implications of PAX9 gene mutations and variations in dental anomalies has been explored, emphasizing its clinical relevance in understanding the etiology of various orodental diseases. Different mutations in different exons of PAX9 gene has been detected which leads to various consequences. Conditions such as dental agenesis (hypo-dontia and oligodontia), malocclusions, cleft lip and palate, impacted teeth etc. are associated with the mutations in PAX9 gene. Identification of various mutations of PAX9 gene can empowers the clinicians to deliver more precise, personalized, and effective care, ultimately improving the oral health outcomes and quality of life for individuals worldwide.

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